

Supplemental Figure 2 (S2). Gene marker sensitivity (% amplifying and having sequence identity/total parasite populations) of *T. cruzi* populations from major Neotropical Mexican triatomine species: *Triatoma dimidiata* Hg1 (N=38), *Triatoma dimidiata* Hg2 (N=308), *Triatoma dimidiata* Hg3 (N=41), *Triatoma pallidipennis* (N=260), *Triatoma phyllosoma* (N=59).

